

Supply Chain Transformation of Hewlett-Packard Incorporated: A Crucial Step to Increase SCM Performance

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Abstract

Supply chains is a process in fulfilling customers' demand that include all parties engaged in either directly or through indirect means. This includes all the activities related to new product operations, marketing, development, finance, distribution, and customer service, among others. Every supply chain aims to maximize the overall value produced. Supply chain surplus or value produced difference of value between final product and supply chain costs incurs in meeting the request of the customers. This paper digs into examination of HP's supply chain management approach. It examines the company's approach to supply chain optimization. The data is gathered from secondary data and assesses the overall performance of its supply chain management. By analyzing HP's supply chain management practices, this paper wanted to uncover potential improvements in HP's supply chain management. In facing the dynamic demand, HP also keep improving its supply chain by some strategy which become its supply chain design. First, being resilience by expanding company capabilities by establish new factories in new countries and improve company technology so that company can keep up to date with the trend. Next, HP being flexible by building long-term relationship with many suppliers and having multiple distribution network strategy. After that, agile by providing many products that can fit customer demand. Last, sustainable by creating standard in supply chain process regarding sustainability in process. Hence, HP can strive in the aggressive competition and in facing the uncertainty.

Key words: Supply Chain Management (SCM), SCM Transformation, SCM Performance, Hewlett-Packard

Introduction

Supply chain management encompasses many activities such as planning, execution, and control of the goods and services from suppliers to customers (Chopra, et al., 2017). It looks more complex compared to what it seems. It involves many individuals and groups that are interconnected, each playing a crucial role in ensuring the timely and efficient process to deliver products to meet customer demand. The correct items cannot be purchased, manufactured, moved, or sold in the right quantities overnight (Wu et al., 2016). With short-term demand, pressure of rivalry, technological solution and pressure of costcausing today's market is marked has an distinguished history in supply chain management of Hewlett-Packard Incorporated (HP Inc.) that has demonstrated an optimized supply chainstrategy and keep improving its supply chain strategy in adapting to evolving market dynamics. However, the transformation process of Hewlett-Packard (HP) to achieve the target is not smooth sailing. There are many challenges HP has faced ever since it established the company after the split up from Hewlett-Packard Company (HP Co.) into HP Inc. and Hewlett-PackardEnterprise (HPE) in 2015 causing the annual revenue of the company in 2022 to decrease to 62,910 million USD from 63,460 million USD in 2021 (Macrotrends, 2023). One of the challenges HP faces is the shortage of the components to fulfill the dynamic demand.

It was found by HP that it relies heavily on the third party as the source of the components. This causes component shortages. Accompanied by fluctuating demand that causes excess supply company it causes a decline in 2022 revenue and might continue to 2023 revenue. The reasons for components shortage: certain components result from strong demand hence particular components experiencing shortage. The company has capacity constraints which make the company unable to store all the components needed. Furthermore, when the company needed the component supplier unable to produce it because of financial weaknesses that made the supplier unable to produce the components needed. Additionally, there are also dispute with suppliers that also HP customer.

When the shortages and delays last longer the price of the components might rise exponentially which will reduce the revenue. Quality issues happened to meet the demand, because company can only accept components of acceptable quality. And the worst is when there is no component available at all. The shortages and delays resulted in lost time-sensitive sales which company unable to launch the product. There will be freight costs incurred because the company must store the delayed product. Last, the company also cannot pass the increase in price to customers due to the delay or shortages.

This paper digs into examination of HP's supply chain management approach. It examines the company's approach to supply chain optimization. The data is gathered from secondary data and assesses the overall performance of its supply chain management. By analyzing HP's supply chain management practices, this paper wanted to uncover potential improvements in HP's supply chain management.

The detailed purpose of this study:

1. To know the decision phase of Hewlett-Packard's supply chain.
2. To understand the process view of Hewlett-Packard's supply chain.
3. To know how Hewlett-Packard achieves the strategic fit.
4. To analyze the way of Hewlett-Packard in expanding its strategic scope.
5. To know how the distribution network of Hewlett-Packard.
6. To understand the online sales of Hewlett-Packard.
7. To analyze the performance level of Hewlett-Packard's supply chain.

Literature Review

Supply chain concept

Supply chains is a process in fulfilling customers' demand that include all parties engaged in either directly or through indirect means, according to Chopra, et al. (2017). This includes all the activities related to new product operations, marketing, development, finance, distribution, and customer service, among others. Every supply chain aims to maximize the overall value produced. Supply chain surplus or value produced difference of value between final product and supply chain costs incurs in meeting the request of the customers.

Global supply chain movements not only comprises components but additionally also encompass finished items and raw materials in the service as well as manufacturing industries among multinational companies looking to improve company performance (Gereffi and Lee, 2012; Um and Han, 2020). Hence, efficiency and minimizing cost being searched supply chainmanagement. The process of satisfying customers through the supply chain with generate profititself (Chopra, et al., 2017). Supply chain involves many parties that connected such as customers, retailers, wholesalers, distributors, manufacturers, and suppliers. All supply chain functions within organizations in supply chain is to fulfil the demand of customer. Supply chainproduct flow showed through the movements of products from suppliers until it reached the hands of end consumers. There is a constant flow of products, finances, and information at every stage in the process that keep changing in supply chain. For instance, customers an integral part of supply chain purchasing products in an online website of the company. Customers will receive information regarding the products such as pricing, product types, andproduct availability. Once the the customer deciding on the product, the customer will check out and pay for the product. Customers can check the order progress, while the company, through the information will fill the customer request.

Hugos (2018) stated that efficient supply chain management in a corporation requires simultaneous increases in customer service levels and internal operating efficiencies in the supply chain. It is an ongoing process of the company in doing organizational change. It might cause a company to create new roles, change the organizational structure, or develop new technology and skills. Supply chains that fail to adapt to the changing environment will hurt performance significantly (Chopra, et al., 2017). The complicated supply chain supply resulted in company must be able to manage supply chains by ensuring the flow of information, products, and fundsdoes not get interrupted and able to achieve the aims of supply chains.

Process view of supply chain

Cycle time, in particular, has been routinely utilized to assess the efficiency of the order management process (Zhao, et al. 2021). Long cycle time is undesirable in most industrial systems because it reduces prediction accuracy, causes the shipment got delayed, and increases supply chain costs (Monden, 2012; Stalk & Hout, 1990; Zhao et al. 2021). Due to that many companies desired to minimize the cycle time process.

1) Customer order cycle

When orders are prepared, processed, and sent, the orders is part of the customer order cycle (Rodrigue, 2023). By reducing client order lead time, you may provide better customer service by delivering orders faster (Blocher and Chhaged, 2008). Currently, there are many businesses using electronic business (e-business). A more coordinated material flow network is created by e-business information flow from client orders to manufacturing, storage, distribution, and delivery (Feng Yin and Pheng Khoo, 2007). With e-business companies can simplify the process of the customer order cycle.

2) Replenishment cycle

A word used in inventory management to describe the process of replenishing goods from a central place (Monash, 2023). This approach frequently includes the creation of quantitatively based inventory models intended to optimize the resupply process. According to Ng, et al. (1997) and Asghari, et al. (2022) factors that influencing procurement cycle time consist of three. is the assessment of suppliers is the first factor to consider. It entails selecting providers who can deliver the desired good as soon as possible. The timing of the procurement procedure within the organization is the next consideration. It is when a buy request becomes a purchase order. The last consideration is supplier-firm relationships. In which how many suppliers option company has.

3) Manufacturing cycle

Manufacturing. It entails diverse flows of finished and semi-finished commodities that are sector-specific (Rodrigue, 2023). The manufacturing process results in the goods that will be processed again or finished and will be sold by the company. The goal of the product manufacturing cycle is to provide more goods-related knowledge as well as a platform that can be shared to facilitate the creativity, association, and dissemination of goods-related information (Zhang, et al., 2017; Majeed, et al, 2019). This will facilitate the improvement of company efficiency. By sharing product-related information, the probability of meeting customer demand is also high.

4) Procurement cycle

A continuous improvement process for planning, delivering, implementing, and learning from procurement strategy is the procurement cycle (Mena, et al., 2021). The company must learn from past activities and decisions to improve the process of procurement using a procurement strategy. By connecting and coordinating the

organization strategies of various divisions in firms with day-to-day activities of procurement is the strategic of procurement cycle (Mena, et al., 2021). Improved coordinated company in the procurement cycle will achieve the targeted objectives.

Strategic fit

When competitive method and supply chain tactics, both in the firms has compatible goals is the requirements of strategic fit (Chopra, et al., 2017). In a kind that assists the company business strategy, the supply chain required to answer to the requirements of market (Hugos, 2018). Company strategies defined depend on products and services that will satisfy customer needs which will be prioritized based on customer. The company has functions such as marketing, operations, distributions, et cetera. These functions have their roles and it owns strategy. These strategies must support each other. Companies must correspond to their decisions with their strategy, goals, and mission, as well as reduce costs in the long run (Meixell and Gargeya, 2005; Um and Han, 2020).

According to Chopra, et al. (2017) there are three steps that are fundamental to achieve strategic fit: first, company must understand the customer. There is uncertainty in customer demand and supply chain. By comprehending the need of the customer company can identify the extend of demand unpredictability and the company able to prepare the supply chain strategy. Second, supply chain capabilities must be understood by the company. It is by understand what supply chain of the company current capabilities in terms of responsiveness and efficiency. Sending the correct combination of efficiency and responsiveness based on customer's need is crucial for firms (Hugos, 2018). Like quality defect, delay on shipment in world supply chain, as well as high levels of inventory are the list of potential internal risks; however, with supply chain resilience, the operation is under control. (Gunasekaran et al., 2015).

Third, strategic fit is achieved. The company must alter the supply chain if the mismatch between customer demand and supply chain is particularly big. Moreover, to ensure the right level of responsiveness or efficiency it must ensure roles on each different stage. It is in order to achieve the desired level of strategy the company wants. And does not let one stage act only to achieve its own goal. Well-aligned Supply chain management practices that among partners are part of long-term competitive advantage that comes from supply chain partners, which are difficult to replicate (Prajogo et al., 2016).

Driver of supply chain performance

According to Chopra, et al. (2017) there are a total of six factors that influence supply chain performance. These drivers are: (1). *Facilities*. It involves where product is produced, warehouse, product is assembled, or fabricated, and distribution centres. It includes the decision whether dedicated, flexible, or combination for the production process. i.e., the decision of warehouse and distribution centers whether purely as storage facilities or for assembly or cross-docking. For instance, the company increases the number of warehouses in order to be closer to customer and increase responsiveness. (2). *Inventory*. It plays role in directing all raw materials, work in process, and finished goods to match supply and demand

in supply chain. The decision of inventory is between supply chain efficiency and responsiveness. A high level of inventory means high responsiveness but it carries high costs. While lowering the cost will be high in efficiency but low in responsiveness. Constraints on resources that apply to all purchased products Warehouse limitations (Jackson & Munson, 2019). Understanding the trade-offs between raise in capacity costs and possible decreases in buying and/or inventory linked to costs related with capacity expansion decisions is crucial in organizing warehouse (Jackson & Munson, 2019). (3). *Transportation*. In supply chain, the transportation will create space value for the products. Size, type, and location of transportation fleet were the decisions involved in transportations. Supply chain responsiveness and efficiency receiving high impact on. Being able to move freely or effortlessly moved is what called as mobility (Cambridge Dictionary, 2020). Because transportation can only exist if passengers, freight, and information are moved around, the specific goal of transportation is to meet a demand for mobility (Rodrigue, 2020). As a result, companies often develop mobility needs that must be met. That is the driving force behind managing transportation in the supply chain. (4). *Information*. Such as facilities, inventory, transportation, costs, prices of the goods, and customers are the information that connected to the supply chain. This will connect all supply chain and aid the coordination in supply chain. The decisions related with supply chain drivers is uses information as the foundation (Hugo, 2018). The decision in this driver such as forecasting demand, choosing pull or push system, size of information technology (IT), and how many information shared between partner of supply chain. This will be affecting company efficiency and responsiveness. The possible benefits of using information technology such as shorten the supply chain networks is deeply realized by supply chain participants (Crandall, et al., 2015). (5). *Sourcing*. the decision of who will do various activities in supply chain such as selection of supplier, producer, or distributor. The level of efficiency and responsiveness of a company on every stage of supply chain will be affected. For example, company decide to produce its product in a country with low labor cost but since the market is not exactly on that country so company must add more cost in transportation. (6). *Pricing*. The decision on the amount that customer need to pay for the offering goods and services. Price concerned about the impact towards the behavior of consumer. The greater the quantity of goods produced, the lower the unit cost, which means the company benefits from economies of scale and can reduce costs. Company uses pricing strategy that depend of efficiency or responsiveness strategy of company. Efficiency usually targeting customer that price driven while responsiveness is not price driven.

Distribution network

According to Chopra, et al. (2017) distribution is the stage of moving products through the supply and storage chain from suppliers to customers. It is like a raw material from supplier to manufacturers, from manufacturers to retailers and to the end of consumer. Company overall profitability is significantly stimulated by distribution since it is directly influencing the cost in supply chain and customer value. Thus, designing distribution network that appropriate is important to achieve low cost to high responsiveness in supply chain objectives.

The decision that company must choose is to prioritize responsiveness or efficiency of the company. Applying responsiveness strategy means the faster the product arrives the more costly it is. Meanwhile, when the company choose to use efficiency strategy means that company might slow on delivery but the cost reduced. However, everything also based on the product characteristics since some product might considered fragile. Some product also considered urgent and some product can be easily predicted.

Company also needs to manage wholesalers and retailers to meet the need of the company. Company can directly connect with retailers but other need distributor to connect. Due to that company need to set a standard price in order preventing market price of the product become uncontrollable.

Supply chain performance

Because today's rivalry is no longer between enterprises, measuring supply chain performance is critical (Sahay, 2003; Galankashi and Rafiei, 2022). To find and measure performance measures, indicators, or metrics is an old definition of what performance measurement seeks (Galankashi and Helmi, 2016; Galankashi and Rafiei, 2022). Financial performance improved by using effective performance measurement methods (Galankashi and Rafiei, 2022). More specifically, it is widely acknowledged that there is high level of impact of the efficiency of supply chain of the firms on firms' financial performance (Shi and Yu, 2013). Supply chain efficiency improves company performance in terms of investment efficiency, operational efficiency, market share, revenue growth, labor cost reduction, and shareholder value (Christopher and Ryals, 1999; Li, et al., 2006; Hong and Najmi, 2020). Which mean the when the revenue shows raising trend the revenue means a good performance in supply chain however if it is showing downward trend, it is bad for the company. Historically, inventories are a common measure of manufacturing processes (Kwak, 2019). Inventory turnover percentages are unbiased, public, as well as indicative of efficiency in operation (Kwak, 2019). Therefore, in this study will quantify the performance of supply chain of HP, inventory changes used.

Results and Discussions

Company Profile of HP

HP established in 2015 after the split of HP into HP and HPE. Back to the history, according to HP (2023), founded in 1934 by Bill Hewlett and Dave Packard, HP is an American

multinational information technology company. HP becoming a giant technology company from America. Two people with shared vision and mission create their first product and

oscillator called “HP Model 200A from a garage shop.” As the years progressed, Hewlett-Packard's reputation for quality and innovation grew. HP as global leader in IT industry committed to providing its customer with best possible goods and services. However, in 2015 HP decided to split-up in facing the change happened in the market and to compete more effectively. HPE is focused on business technology infrastructure, software and services while HP will focus on personal systems and printing businesses. Splitting up HP into two companies, HP losing the benefits it can gain previously as one big company. But HP still continues to strive to improve the condition especially in its supply chain situation.

Supply chain decision phases of HP

The core strategy of HP is to improve its core business, innovate and develop new goods, services and solutions, expand into nearby regions, and achieve organic and inorganic growth (HP, 2023). In facing the challenges that happen HP continues to develop its supply chain. According to a press release by HP (2022), in today's dynamic business environments, with the need of geographically diverse footprints HP realized the importance of resilience and flexible supply chain while improving the sustainability for customer and the communities.

In expecting unexpected damaging events by actively designing as well as drawing the network of supply chain while maintaining control of structure and operations but responding flexibly to deficiencies, with subsequent processes as cheap as possible compared to previous events, hence giving a firm a competitive edge is called supply chain resilience (Ponis, et al., 2012). When supply chain lacks resilience then a company will have fragile sustainability (Ahern, 2013). HP is able to recognize the challenges and is proactively improving its supply chain to balance the resilience and sustainability. To focus on building a robust supply chain that can withstand disruption by shifting supplier partnerships is one of the requirements.

An agile supply chain tactic implemented by firms, is near to supply chain responsive strategy, pursuing a swift response towards demand, while improving flexibility, permitting the firms to exploit changes in unanticipated markets. (Mason-Jones et al., 2000; Zimmermann, et al., 2020). HP (2022) realized the importance of having agility in supply chain. Reacting faster to unpredictable changes in supply and demand clearly refers to supply chain agility (Christopher and Peck, 2004). HP started embracing digital transformation. HP is deploying advanced digital tools on its entire value chain. This is in order to be more responsive in addressing potential issues, make data-driven decisions, optimize inventory management which will improve overall supply chain performance. This will give more benefits to HP and customers. Due to that the HP target is to be faster, more accurate, and more agile in a changing world. Agile as well as lean strategy mainly to meet the customer requirements; meanwhile lean in particular seeks efficiency and reduction in cost more compared to agile while agile concentrates on information, time, and trade-offs in fluid and creative surroundings as knowledge (Nakandala and Lau, 2019).

Process view of supply chain of HP

HP's Cycle view

Customer order cycle: HP provides many products such as personal computer (PC), printers, printing supplies (ink cartridges, toner cartridges, and paper), and software. Additionally, HP also provide service for IT support, consulting, training, and financing and leasing options for its products and services. HP initially heavily relied on traditional retail channels and physical stores. However, in the rise of information and technology HP now primarily invest in e-commerce and omnichannel strategies include user-friendly online store, mobile apps, offering faster ordering, real-time ordering, and personalized recommendation (HP, 2023). In daily operation of HP currently adopting strategy to create its own customers. For instance, company able to monitors the usage of customer's printer ink and before it runs out, HP will send the new ink cartridge. This program called as an Instant Ink program. Hence, customers do not need to place any order since the printers will does it by itself. Hence, this strategy also called as machine customers (Gartner, 2022).

Replenishment cycle: HP currently using demand-driven replenishment, using real-time sales data, analytics, and machine learning to forecast demand and maximizing the levels of inventory. Due to this, the cycle times become faster, stockouts were reduced, and cash flow also improved (HP, 2021). Demand-driven replenishment entails multi-echelon inventory planning, execution, and optimization to safeguard and encourage flow while allowing businesses to become increasingly demand-driven (SAP, 2023). One of the instances is HP in Managed Print Services (MPS) contracts offers just-in-time delivery for its toner/ink cartridge. HP use a Data Collection Agent to remote monitoring of cartridge levels. HP will ship cartridges during the first 30 days when 18 days printing days last and the supply only remain 7% (depends on the devices) (HP, 2023).

Manufacturing cycle: Currently, HP uses Lean, Six Sigma, and security evaluations to analyze process discoveries and industry-specific demands. HP also with strict procedure, own HP Enterprise Test Lab that ensuring the performance of the products produced by HP as a system (HP, 2023). Lean manufacturing stresses waste reduction, continuous improvement, and a coordinated or integration of material flows within the company, eventually incorporating first-tier suppliers and customers. (Leong, et al., 2022). Six Sigma is a quality-control system used by corporations to decrease errors and enhance processes (Hayes, 2023). Six Sigma is an enterprise-wide philosophy that includes suppliers, employees, and customers (Leong, et al., 2022). It underscores the firm commitment to strive for greatness in the production of products and services which consumers want.

Procurement cycle: HP also using electronic procurement (e-procurement) method which streamlines the procurement process of the customers. Customer can do online shopping for company enterprises and public sector professionals. Customer can receive end-to-end control over prices, catalogues, and transaction (HP, 2023). By using e-procurement company able to provide several benefits such as trackability, cost savings, time savings, more accurate, real-time use, mobility, et cetera (Leong, et al., 2022). By responding quickly to changes in the business surroundings, providing services and goods depending on customer needs, and leveraging new ideas and resources agility contributed by the procurement process of the firm's (Nicoletti, 2018; Asghari, et al., 2022). HP using sustainable procurement strategy. HP paid attention to the effect on social and environmental from the supplier, type and quantity of the goods and services bought by the company. The procurement criteria must be fair and equitable, based on aspects such as sustainability throughout the goods and services' whole life cycles. For example, at the point of purchase, the energy expenses to operate the gadget, as well as the end of first life, security, and environmental and societal issues, must all be considered (HP, 2023). The procurement function assists with organizational resources primarily through supply market knowledge and skills (Mena, et al., 2021). Resources are extremely crucial for company. With procurement handled well HP able to use it to improve company sustainability. HP that also facing shortages found that supplying components on-time and complete become urgent issue. Hence, HP also using circular economy (CE) ecosystem.

Figure 1. The linear economy Source: HP (2023)

CE is a system that generate process by slowing down, closing, and restricting material and energy cycle which reduce resource entry and waste, emissions, and energy leakage are reduced (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017; Hazen, et al., 2021). From the figure 2, it can be found started from waste that become resource from end user, transferred to three possible options. First, if the resource can be maintained repaired, and upgraded the products. Second, if the goods able to be remarketed, restored, reused, and remarketed, then will be manufactured by manufacturer into finished or semi-finished goods. Third, materials will be recovered and recycled through suppliers. The suppliers, manufacturer, and technician connected respectively from up to the bottom and the finished goods later will be used again by end user. For example, in the transition process from purchasing products and services like managed print services it will give huge benefits of sustainability. The materials or products used as long as possible with maintenance to maintain its condition. Hence, this will reduce throwing resources and polluting land, air, and water.

HP shifting the process from the linear LE to CE (HP, 2021). To HP procurement is the driver

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in the transition process from linear economy to circular economy. CE implemented by HP with sustainability in mind. While LE lacking in sustainability.

Strategic fit and competitive strategy of HP

To establish a strategic fit, HP must coordinate its whole supply chain and competitive strategy. The goal is what mentioned already in supply chain design which are being resilience, flexible, agile but keep sustainable. According to Zimmermann et al. (2020), establishing an adequate supply chain strategy is required for organizations operating in the market. HP (2023) main competitive strategy of diversification. HP known to has strong portfolio. HP as mentioned above focused on Personal System and Printing but also provide services and consultation for its product. HP create Future Ready portfolio. HP sought to expand its portfolio through gaming, hybrid systems, workforce services and solutions, consumer subscription, industrial graphics, and 3D industries under this plan. To expand the portfolio, HP employ customer insights, big data, and analytics (HP, 2023). big data used by HP to gain customer insight and analyze and maximize it to achieve company goal. With insight it will drive employee's performance and business operations. For instance, monitoring device health, performance, and security and addressing any needs based on actionable insights and analytics. This will create opportunities and proactively avoid disruption in supply chain which will generate more productivity. With digital technology employee also able to use digital scorecards, surveys, and benchmarking. This strategy is in order to achieve the future ready plan of hybrid system. HP realized that most of the workers prefer to work flexibly

Sustainability. In order to align supplier with company goal of sustainability. HP presents some requirements for supplier to follow. HP required supplier to align with HP goals. For instances, HP provide procurements requirements that consider sustainable aspects. HP expect

the suppliers can align their decision making with HP social and environmental goals, policies, and priorities. HP also considering more companies that has ecolabels for IT suppliers (HP, 2023). HP also presents targets in order to achieve sustainability of the company. For instances, achieving net zero carbon across supply chain by 2040, create sustainable portfolio in the technology industry while generating economy by 50% reducing GHG emissions by 2030, and zero deforestation. Everything HP plan is under the compliance of governments regulations. Environmental performance reporting will demonstrate the transparency and reputation of firm managers (Lukman, et al., 2020). In monitoring the performance of activities to achieve the goal in sustainability, HP use sustainability scorecard tool which consist 60% audit performance, 13% environmental reporting, 6% minerals disclosure, and 21% other social and environmental topics (Figure 3). This tools result will be discussed between suppliers and HP as part of evaluation business process (HP Sustainability and Compliance Center, 2023).

Figure 3. HP sustainability scorecard
Source: HP (2023)

Understanding supply chain capabilities of HP: To adjust, flourish, and adapt in the face of disruptive change is part of the ability of a corporation or group of corporate units is referred to as supply chain resilience (Fiksel et al, 2015; Um and Han, 2020). In order for HP to be resilience in supply chain design, HP not only need multi-source components but also need to own manufacturing capacity with strategic location to handle the components and to handle the possible future issue. To own the capabilities, HP invest in current sites, and some alternate locations for producing some components to create flexibility and prevent risk for the customers. HP also invest in build new facilities to create capacity in the areas where HP underdeveloped (HP, 2023). HP also create options for customers, deliver the needs of the customers, and continuously adapt with the changes to remain competitive the market. HP need to evaluate and improve in order to achieve the results over time. This is because, existing risks associated with suppliers, manufacturers, and customers might have an effect on firms' capacity to manage risks and gain the advantages of supply chain resilience capabilities (Um and Han, 2020). Thus, HP also need and grateful for the great supply chain teams and partners that capable to work to achieve the goals. One of the cases, HP in China has been there for 40 years. HP have built a huge manufacturing ecosystem which is important for future global supply chain. These capabilities built together with investment on the economic and social development of China. With 12,000 channel partners, distribute the goods and services, R&D operations in Shanghai. On top of that, investment in environmental sustainability and digital equity (Nicholas, 2022).

Organizations that engage in commercial operations using or connected to natural resources are obligated to have responsibility for society and the environment. (Murjiyanto, et al., 2023). HP build capability by helping suppliers to develop social and environmental responsibility (SER) performance using programs and partnerships with non-government organizations (NGOs), training partners, as well as government institutions. While suppliers mainly focusing on employee's empowerment and management system development (HP, 2016).

HP in achieving strategic fit

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a. Suppliers

HP Realized that they are heavily depend on third-party suppliers. This is due to suppliers' ability to provide enough quantities and key components, products, and services with better price compared to in-house decision and on-time in meeting the delivery schedules of HP products and services. Cutting expenses mainly dealt in strategic sourcing, its foundation is the formation of long-term, win-win agreements with key suppliers to provide buyers a competitive advantage (Mutanya, 2021).

However, because of this reliance, it caused issue with shortages of components because company cannot create it in-house and contract have been signed (HP, 2023). On the other hand, when long-term commercial relationship with a supplier is secured, a consumer may benefit from the supplier's relation-specific investments that have characteristics unique to the buyer (Merckx and Chaturvedi, 2020).

b. Manufacturers

HP has a large number of outsourced manufacturers (Oms) all around the world to produce its goods (HP, 2023). This is attributed to increased production efficiency and shorter time to market for HP-designed goods. Numerous Oms were utilized to retain the flexibility of the supply chain as well as manufacturing operations. HP also under agreement can resell the product produced by third-party under HP brand. Furthermore, from many vendors, HP produced finished products from components and sub-assemblies it (HP, 2023).

According to Stravrulaki and Davis (2010) and Ribas, et al., (2018) related to product characteristic one of them is make-to-order which can switch between goods as long as they are created from the same raw resources. Building goods to order and establishing product order strategy was another method used by HP manufacturer, it is the same with inventory strategy. This is to achieve efficiency in manufacturer and logistics by manufacturing significant amount of fundamental product configurations. Hence, HP able to meet the hardware and software demand of customers' requirements (HP, 2023).

c. Retailers

A person, shop, or firm that sells items to the general public is retailer (Cambridge Dictionary, 2023). HP (2023) strategy is also to sell their product through retailers. Retailers then sell the products focused to public consumers and small-medium businesses (SMBs). In the retail industry, innovations typically involve adjustments to products and procedures that either cut prices or improve efficiency (Huang and Rachael, 2018). Retailers also possible to give value added benefits to the customer outside what company provides. However, retailers also often to sell HP products together with product of competitors and non-original supplies. Some might highlight the non-original supplies and if it is continued, it will hard HP financial performance especially if the product offered by retailers is from HP exact competitors.

Expanding strategic fit scope of HP

Intraoperation scope

HP manufacturers choosing to heavily relied on outsourcing in manufacturing components of HP product because it is less cost and increase company efficiency (HP, 2023). By outsource the components comparing to maintaining in-house production, HP able to significantly cut costs of the company. After the components from many suppliers gathered HP only need to check and assemble the components into finished goods. This also mean the efficiency of the company is rising and company also able to reach more customer from knowing and maintaining relationship with suppliers.

Intrafunctional view

HP letting IT share information gathered using software to inventory, transportation, and warehouse management work together aligned to minimize the cost which is increase company efficiency (HP, 2023). HP able minimizing cost by avoiding the lost caused by inaccurate information. All the function glued together by IT and make them able to collaborate more significantly. Providing data on evolving consumer tastes and consumption habits identified at the point of sale by downstream supply chain participants like retailers, for instance, might help upstream supply chain partners revise their manufacturing and distribution plans (Fawcett et al., 2007; Rajaguru & Matanda, 2019). As a result, enhancing the capabilities of supply chain is crucial to organizational-level competitiveness as well as productivity increase in relevancy in supply chain by sharing abilities and assets (Rai et al., 2006; Wu et al., 2006; Rajaguru & Matanda, 2019).

Interfunctional scope

HP famous with its innovation in technology, hence HP heavily invested on its R&D. Since the investment high in R&D company try to streamline the cost by outsource and build long-term relationship with the suppliers (HP, 2023). Hence, HP able to increase the company overall profits from the technology innovation value itself which is in line with HP diversification strategy in its portfolio. In this regard, several authors discovered that interfunctional coordination (IC) can result in customer-driven new ideas (Altinay, 2010; Ruiz-Alba, et al., 2020).

Intercompany scope

HP and Microsoft doing a strategic alliance in order to improve the profits. Both HP and Microsoft join together in integrate hardware and software solution. Microsoft also used as operating system on HP personal computer (HP, 2023). HP able to increase supply chain surplus because both firms, instead of competing aggressively in making each own PC with operating system, both combined two company product and create better collaboration products. Risks and costs may be shared between partners which will resulted in access new markets, new skills, and even affect competitive dynamics when they collaborate on innovation. (Tyler and Steensma, 1995; Veugelers, 1998; Song, et al., 2021).

Agile intercompany scope

Expectations from consumers regarding product assortments and service, as well as regulatory demands for correct data and company demands for "more or less" are all driving efforts to enhance business performance along with customer service (Huang and Rachael, 2018). As the trend on technology industry keep changing HP must agile in providing the products to meet the demand of the customer. HP planned to move from single-source components product to product that can suit many components that multi-sourced. As HP facing shortages in components, HP still maintaining high level connections with many suppliers. (HP, 2023). HP realize that the demand is very dynamic that HP need to be agile in providing the product to the customers. HP sets standards to the supplier in order to maintain the product quality and company brand image.

Distribution networks of HP

Company needs combination of HP (2023) distribute its products and services direct and indirect to consumer and SMBs through:

- a. distributors that sell supply HP product to resellers;
- b. retailers that primarily focused on consumers and SMBs;
- c. resellers with their very own extra value goods or services;
- d. and integrators of systems and corporate mediators that assist in various levels of services as service solutions.

With multi-tier distribution network to reach potential customer is a complex process. HP realize the distinct risk followed in each method and gross margins and might failed in manage the best balance of distribution model. Adjusting orders and seasonal fluctuation in end-customer must be done by distribution. Traceability refers to ability information in supply chain collected which also called as capability (Sunny, et al., 2020). While supply chain transparency is defined as the degree in which every stakeholder has access to, the product-related information that they require with no lag, loss, distortion, or noise and common understanding (Sunny, et al., 2020). With multi-tiered channel in indirect distribution method, HP receive less visibility into inventory, demand, and pricing trends. Thus, managing multi-tiered channel inventory and predicting customer demand become increasingly challenging in implementing the traceability and transparency.

Online sales of HP

HP manage the customer using direct online sales by primarily targeting consumers and SMBs. This direct channel managed by HP provides fast and free delivery, warranty that its product is 100% original products (no imitation), convenience 14 day returns, free consultation, and price match guarantee (HP, 2023).

HP with omnichannel strategy using online-to-offline stores (O2O) which customers can come to flagship stores offline but able to experience personalized shopping experience by connect offline stores with online stores across the countries in Southeast Asia. HP also provides HP live advisors on offline and online stores.

Through online sales, HP able to provide customer service online in two ways. First, live

chats and video call that available 24/7 through the websites. Online sales also enable customers to track the progress of the order which is not only benefiting the customers but also company because company can monitor and ensure that there is no disruption in delivery process (HP, 2023).

Daniel Martinez, Director of Support Solutions for HP mentioned that loyalty increased a lot driven by customer service which mean better customer service more business to sustain HP. Due to the complex products and services that need HP supports, HP saw the potential for artificial intelligence (AI) in creating better support to customer and agent. Customer are able to do self-service which increase the effectiveness of its support agents. Collaborating with

solution for customer service by Microsoft Dynamics 365 AI, HP provide the virtual agents that were also installed in every HP computer. When virtual agents cannot solve the problem completely, the call will direct customers to the live agents. With AI the agents able to receive the all the issues and problem faced by the customers such as diagnostic results, the condition of system, and the serial number. And now from 15% to 20% issues now 70% to 80% issues solved by artificial intelligence (Microsoft, 2016).

Measuring supply chain performance of HP

Mentioned in introduction, HP facing shortages in components which resulting in lower revenue in 2022 compared to 2021. In comparing the revenue of HP between 2015 to 2022, overall HP still rising in revenue compared to the early years after split up of the HP Co. The recent data of HP from 63,460 million USD in 2021 to 62,910 million USD in 2022. The highest revenue of HP Inc. was in 2021 with 63,460 million USD and the lowest revenue is in 2016 with 48,238 million USD (Figure 4).

Figure 4. HP Inc. Annual Revenue from 2015 to 2022 Source: Macrotrends (2023)

Next, comparing the revenue between the biggest competitors of HP which are Dell and Lenovo in 2015 to 2022. HP Inc. and Dell seems not very different in revenue during 2015 to 2016. While Dell started to rising up its revenue significantly more that HP Inc. and

Lenovo. HP Inc. itself only slightly rising compared to the significant rise of Dell. While Lenovo falling behind in revenue compare to HP Inc. and Dell until in 2022 Lenovo take the second place from HP Inc. in amount of revenue with 71,618 and 62,910 respectively. Able to overcome HP in revenue shows that HP performance declined compared to the other competitors (Figure 5).

REVENUE IN MILLION USD (HP INC., LENOVO, & DELL)

Figure 5. Revenue in Billion Dollars (HP Inc., Lenovo, & Dell) Source: Macrotrends (2023)

Furthermore, the decrease in HP performance can also be seen from its inventory turnover. HP has slight rise from 2015 to 2017, from 7.3x to 8.3x. The year 2017 also the year where HP inventory turnover was the highest, after that HP started to going down consecutively in inventory turnover. From 2018 to 2022 it can be seen that there is no any rise in inventory turnover. From 2018, 8.1x to 6.5x, it shows that the supply chain performance of HP declining every year and not in good condition (Figure 6).

HP 2015 - 2022 INVENTORY TURNOVER

Figure 6. HP 2015 – 2022 Inventory Turnover Source: Finbox.com (2023)

In short HP Inc. condition in recent years facing a lot of declines compared to previous year. As well as when being compared to its competitors, HP facing competitors (Dell and Lenovo) that started to rise up significantly and overcome the revenue of HP. Furthermore, inventory turnover that declining a lot without any improvements or comeback make HP supplychain performance become more pessimistic and in passive states.

Conclusion

HP as technological giant company with diversification strategy. High level of product portfolio in personal system and printing makes HP become one of the best supply chain performances in the world by ranked 21 by Gartner in 2023 (Gartner, 2023). Through the analysis above, HP able to grow from a garage company into current company with revenue of more than 60 billion USD is not without great supply chain management. By making a plan to design the supply chain to increase in flexibility, resilience, agility, and sustainability, HP striving for better supply chain.

However, as HP growing, HP meet some sets back in the process of supply chain which causing HP revenue declined compared to previous years and compared to its competitors (Dell and Lenovo). Furthermore, HP also in the position of declining in inventory turnover rate in recent years (2018 to 2022) which sent some alert to the company for the reasons why it facing decline in revenue and turnover. Of course, HP still has more consideration and foundation in facing the declines. HP found several issues and primarily is the shortages in components for producing the goods of the company. However, HP also planning some solutions and improvement to its supply chain.

In detail, the shortages caused by certain components are in short supply as a result of high demand. Due to capacity limits, the company is unable to hold all of the required components. Furthermore, when the company required the component, the supplier was unable to deliver due to financial constraints that prevented the supplier from producing the required components. HP plan to create to design a product that can fit many components. This is to reduce components unavailability by changing it to other components. HP also increasing its portfolio as its competitive strategy. Hence HP need to be innovative in creating product design.

Moreover, there are disagreements with suppliers who are also HP customers. HP try to maintain a long-term relationship with suppliers. Even though there is a downside area such as excess supply and non-cancellable agreement, but the benefits of assurance in receiving components overwhelm the issues. This is also for HP to focus on its core activity which is diversification. Another strategy is short-term agreement but keep the product quality good. However, in the process of implementing it, HP created standards with sustainability objective and ensure the product quality. HP also try to improve the visibility so that customer can be satisfied. This is because if delay happened for a longer period the product quality might got affected.

In facing the dynamic demand, HP also keep improving its supply chain by some strategy which become its supply chain design. First, being resilience by expanding company capabilities by establish new factories in new countries and improve company technology so

that company can keep up to date with the trend. Next, HP being flexible by building long-term relationship with many suppliers and having multiple distribution network strategy. After that, agile by providing many products that can fit customer demand. Last, sustainable by creating standard in supply chain process regarding sustainability in process. Hence, HP can strive in the aggressive competition and in facing the uncertainty.

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